

DATA MANAGEMENT PLAN

Grant Agreement number 21GRD10

Project short name quantiAGREMI

Project full title On farm quantification of ammonia and greenhouse gas emissions from livestock production

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Confidentiality Status:
PU - Public, fully open

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Data Management Plan

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METROLOGY PARTNERSHIP |

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1 Data management plan

1.1 Data summary

Questions	Answers
1 Will you re-use any existing data and what will you re-use them for? State the reasons if re-use of any existing data has been considered but discarded.	<p>This project has re-used internal data from the participants. These data have been used with the purpose of validate the project's results.</p> <p>Re-used data from the scientific literature:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. "Chamau grassland study", containing field measurements of N₂O fluxes, N₂O isotopic composition and soil environmental conditions for use in activity A3.3.2, doi:10.5194/bg-12-2517-2015 2. "Beromuenster grassland study", containing field measurements of N₂O fluxes, N₂O isotopic composition and soil environmental conditions for use in activity A3.3.2, doi: 10.1029/2019GB006505. 3. "GestCO₂ dataset" (https://doi.org/10.15454/FQO7VA) containing raw data and calculations related to emissions and mass budget; re-used by INRAE and LNE in A1.4.2 and A1.5.3; results are given in D2 and D4; this dataset provided by INRAE was not reused in 1.4.3 as in the case studied by VSL the model considered a cattle house with one unique volume while the dataset concerned a poultry house divided in 3 rooms 4. "EVsdata set" also used for the paper "Comparison Methan emissions" (https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy12020381): tracer gas data (SF₆ and SF₅CF₄ concentrations) was re-used and be included in the paper "Comparison 'Tracer ratio method' with 'CO₂ balance'" (in preparation) (A1.4.2). 5. CCCFarming (FACCE ERA-GAS and ERA-NET SUSAN project) dataset was generated by project partners in 60 experimental and commercial dairy cattle farms using the same method (https://cccfarming.eu/results/wp-outputs-deliveries/files/wp1/FinalReport.pdf).
2 What types and formats of data will the project generate or re-use?	<p>The project has generated data as follow:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Numerical data in CSV, TXT and MS Excel format • Text description data in Markdown format <p>The project has re-used data as follow:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Numerical data in CSV, TXT and MS Excel format
3 What is the purpose of the data generation or re-use and its relation to the objectives of the project?	<p>The data generated and re-used have been from measurements, calibrations, comparisons, modelling and validations. They have been used in meeting the project's objectives and in conference and peer reviewed publications.</p> <p>Data have been generated by the consortium in order to meet objectives 1 - 4. Measurement and calibration data result from objectives 1, 2 and 4 and comparison and validation data from objectives 1 and 3.</p> <p>Data generated</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dataset 1: Data from the intercomparison of dynamic dry and

	<p>wet NH₃ gas calibration standards. The data was generated to show the feasibility of generating dry and wet traceable reference gas mixtures at amount fractions relevant for the quantification of NH₃ emissions, using for that purpose portable dynamic generators that can provide on-site (i.e., livestock housing) calibrations. This data was used to achieve objective 1 (for activities A1.2.1 to A1.2.4). The Zenodo link will be provided upon paper acceptance.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dataset 2: "NH₃ field fluxes". The data was generated in activity A3.1.3 to characterize the appropriate technologies for NH₃ flux measurements. This data was used to achieve objective 4. The underlying data will be made available upon paper acceptance. • Dataset 3: "Soil isotopic composition in the vicinity of a Dutch animal housing". The data was generated in activity A3.1.6 to assess the utility of soil organic nitrogen isotopic composition as proxy for the spatial extent of near-field nitrogen deposition. This data was used to achieve objective 4. The Zenodo link to the dataset is https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18544379. The DOI number of the related published paper is: https://doi.org/10.1016/j.jqsrt.2025.109643. • Dataset 4: "Calibration and correction protocol (MATLAB application)". The data was generated in activity A3.2.1 and A3.2.2 to correct / calibrate delta values provided by CRDS analysers. This data was used to achieve objective 4. This dataset is available on https://egusphere.copernicus.org/preprints/2025/egusphere-2025-4954/. This dataset is available for download and use. • Dataset 5: "Field study Zurich". The data was generated in activity A3.2.4 to identify N₂O isotopic composition emitted from agricultural soil. This data was used to achieve objective 4. This dataset is available on https://meta.icos-cp.eu/objects/Gyy707SMePiDDIFUCt8Du2Cq. This dataset is under embargo and will be available for download and preview after 2026-05-31. • Dataset 6: "LandscapeDNDC simulations". The data was generated in activities A3.3.1 to A3.3.3 to improve the parameterization of the bio-geochemical model LandscapeDNDC and to quantify and reduce parameter and input uncertainty. This data was used to achieve objective 4. The underlying data will be made available upon paper acceptance. • Dataset 7: Field campaign in Agroscope (Sept. 2024). The data was generated in activity A1.5.2 and A1.5.4 to compare sensors and emission measurement methods. This data was used to achieve objective 1 and 2. The underlying data will be made available upon paper acceptance. • Dataset 8: Field campaigns in Luke farm (Aug. 2024, Jan. 2025). The data was generated in activity A2.3.2, A2.3.3 and A2.3.4 to
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	<p>compare sensors and emission measurement methods. This data was used to achieve objective 1 and 2. The underlying data will be made available upon paper acceptance to provide public datasets for objective 5, beyond the project.</p> <p>Data re-used</p> <p>From the scientific literature:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. “Chamau grassland study”, containing field measurements of N₂O fluxes, N₂O isotopic composition and soil environmental conditions for use in activity A3.3.2, doi:10.5194/bg-12-2517-2015. This dataset was re-used to achieve objective 4. 2. “Beromuenster grassland study”, containing field measurements of N₂O fluxes, N₂O isotopic composition and soil environmental conditions for use in activity A3.3.2, doi: 10.1029/2019GB006505. This dataset was re-used to achieve objective 4. 3. “GestCO2 dataset” (https://doi.org/10.15454/FQO7VA) containing raw data and calculations related to emissions and mass budget; this dataset was re-used by INRAE and LNE in A1.4.2 and A1.5.3; this dataset was re-used to achieve objective 3; the underlying data and associated calculations will be made available upon paper acceptance. 4. “EVSdata set” also used for the paper “Comparison Methan emissions” (https://doi.org/10.3390/agronomy12020381): tracer gas data (SF₆ and SF₅CF₄ concentrations) was re-used for the comparison of the external tracer-ratio method and the CO₂ balancing method (A1.4.2); calculated emissions values will be made available upon paper acceptance. 5. CCCFarming (FACCE ERA-GAS and ERA-NET SUSAN project) dataset was generated by project partners in 60 experimental and commercial dairy cattle farms using the same method (https://cccfarming.eu/results/wp-outputs-deliveries/files/wp1/FinalReport.pdf). This data was used to achieve objective 1.
4 What is the expected size of the data that you intend to generate or re-use?	<p>The overall size of the data is in the range:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • 200 GB – 1 TB
5 What is the origin/provenance of the data, either generated or re-used?	<p>Data generated in the project</p> <p>The data generated have been from measurements, calibrations and other calculations, comparisons, modelling and validations.</p>

	<ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Dataset 1: Data from the intercomparison of dynamic dry and wet NH₃ gas calibration standards. The data was generated in activity A1.2.1 to A1.2.4 by gravimetric preparation, dynamic preparation based on the permeation method, a laser based spectral method and dynamic preparation based on evaporation • Dataset 2: "NH₃ field fluxes". The data was generated in activity A3.1.3 using the controlled NH₃ release system produced by METAS. UKCEH and KIT. • Dataset 3: "Soil isotopic composition in the vicinity of a Dutch animal housing". The data was generated in activity A3.1.6 to assess the utility of soil organic nitrogen isotopic composition as proxy for the spatial extent of near-field nitrogen deposition. (https://doi.org/10.5281/zenodo.18544379). • Dataset 4: the data for the "Calibration and correction protocol (MATLAB application)" was generated in activity A3.2.1 and A3.2.2 using optical analysers to correct / calibrate delta values provided by CRDS analysers. (https://egusphere.copernicus.org/preprints/2025/egusphere-2025-4954/) • Dataset 5: "Field study Zurich". The data was generated generated in activity A3.2.4 using a chamber system provided by KIT to identify N₂O isotopic composition emitted from agricultural soil. (https://meta.icos-cp.eu/objects/Gyy707SMePiDDIFUCt8Du2Cq) • Dataset 6: "LandscapeDNDC simulations". The data was generated in activities A3.3.1 to A3.3.3 to improve the parameterization of the bio-geochemical model LandscapeDNDC and to quantify and reduce parameter and input uncertainty. • Dataset 7: Field campaign in Agroscope (Sept. 2024). The data was generated in activity A1.5.2 and A1.5.4 by using sensors and methods provided by Agroscope, EMPA, INRAE and LNE. • Dataset 8: Field campaigns in Luke farm (Aug. 2024, Jan. 2025). The data was generated in activity A2.3.2, A2.3.3 and A2.3.4 t by using sensors and methods provided by VTT, Luke, Gasera, Senseair, WR, Vaisala, INRAE and LNE. <p>Re-used data</p> <p>The existing data, originated from several sources, include participant's pre-existing data, data from the scientific literature, real-world measurement data and data from simulation experiments.</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. "Chamau grassland study" data was generated by determining N₂O mole fractions and isotopic composition in the atmospheric
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	<p>surface layer at a high temporal resolution with a modified state of-the-art laser spectrometer connected to an automated N₂O preconcentration unit (doi:10.5194/bg-12-2517-2015).</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 2. “Beromuenster grassland study” data was generated by measuring low N₂O fluxes using combined laser spectroscopy with automated static flux chambers (doi: 10.1029/2019GB006505). 3. “GestCO2 dataset” (https://doi.org/10.15454/FQO7VA) was generated using sensors and methods provided by INRAE, ITAVI and ANSES. 4. “EVSdata set” was generated using GC-ECD and CRDS analytics by Agroscope and Empa 5. CCCFarming (FACCE ERA-GAS and ERA-NET SUSAN project) dataset was generated by project partners in 60 experimental and commercial dairy cattle farms using the same method (https://cccfarming.eu/results/wp-outputs-deliveries/files/wp1/FinalReport.pdf); publishable data according to DMP of CCCFarming will be made available upon acceptance by project partners.
<p>6 To whom might your data be useful ('data utility'), outside your project?</p>	<p>The data are suitable for use by other research groups working on the following topics: gas analysis, gas metrology, agricultural science and soil analysis. It will also be useful for standards committees including ISO/TC 193/SC1 WG25, ISO/TC 158, CCQM-GAWG, TC-MC, SCGA, EMN COO, CEN/TC264 WG41, CEN/TC264 WG42, CEN/TC264 WG11, AFNOR/X43D, WG KTBL EmiMin, EMN POLMO.</p> <p>The data might be useful to Instruments manufacturers, other NMIs/DIs, Governmental and environmental agencies, and citizens</p>

1.2 Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR) Data

1.2.1 Making data findable, including provisions for metadata

Questions	Answers
<p>7 Will data be identified by a persistent identifier?</p>	<p>Yes, each of the project's deposited datasets are identified by:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • DOI • Commit/tag on Git repository • Handle • Other
<p>8 Will rich metadata be provided to allow discovery? What metadata will be created? What disciplinary or general standards will be followed? In case metadata standards do not exist in your discipline, please outline what type of metadata will be created and how.</p>	<p>The metadata created for all of the project's deposited datasets are open under a Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication (CC 0) or equivalent (to the extent legitimate interests or constraints are safeguarded), in line with the FAIR principles (in particular machine-actionable) and provide information at least about the following: datasets (description, date of deposit, author(s), venue and embargo); the European Partnership on Metrology funding; grant project name, acronym and number; licensing terms; persistent identifiers for the dataset, the authors involved in the action, and, if possible, for their organisations and the grant. Where applicable, the metadata include persistent identifiers for related publications and other research outputs.</p>

9 Will search keywords be provided in the metadata to optimise the possibility for discovery and then potential re-use?	Yes, the following search keywords are provided in the metadata to optimise the discovery and potential re-use of the deposited datasets: Ammonia and greenhouse gases, emission monitoring.
10 Will metadata be offered in such a way that it can be harvested and indexed?	Zenodo complies with FAIR principles (https://about.zenodo.org/principles/). The metadata are indexed in a searchable resource. Metadata are licensed under CC0, except for email addresses. All metadata are exported via Open Archives Initiative Protocol for Metadata Harvesting (OAI-PMH) and can be harvested.

1.2.2 Making data accessible

Questions	Answers
Repository:	
11 Will the data be deposited in a trusted repository?	The data and associated metadata, documentation and code are deposited in the trusted open access repository Zenodo (https://zenodo.org).
12 Have you explored appropriate arrangements with the identified repository where your data will be deposited?	No, the data have been uploaded via a standard procedure and require no special arrangements.
13 Does the repository ensure that the data are assigned an identifier? Will the repository resolve the identifier to a digital object?	Yes, Zenodo assigns an identifier (DOI) to each of the project's deposited datasets. The repository resolves the identifier to a digital object.
Data:	
14 Will all data be made openly available? If certain datasets cannot be shared (or need to be shared under restricted access conditions), explain why, clearly separating legal and contractual reasons from intentional restrictions. Note that in multi-beneficiary projects it is also possible for specific beneficiaries to keep their data closed if opening their data goes against their legitimate interests or other constraints as per the Grant Agreement.	<p>All of the data that are needed to validate the results presented in scientific publications will be made openly available as the default unless there is a specific reason not to publish the data.</p> <p>The following data are made publicly available:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data obtained with the permission of third parties, but the third parties have not agreed to make the data publicly available. • Data that discloses the identity of a manufacturer. • Data that compromises the protection of a participant(s) intellectual property. <p>The level of data made available has been considered, for example, pre-processed data have not been provided.</p>
15 If an embargo is applied to give time to publish or seek protection of the intellectual property (e.g. patents), specify why and how long this will apply, bearing in mind that research data should be made available as soon as possible.	<p>The data used in scientific publications, posters and oral communications have been and will be made available for re-use as soon as it is reasonably possible.</p> <p>Data generated</p> <p>Dataset x: "Calibration and correction protocol (MATLAB application)". The data was generated in activity A3.2.1 and A3.2.2 to correct / calibrate</p>

Questions	Answers
	<p>delta values provided by CRDS analysers. This data was used to achieve objective 4. This dataset is available on https://egusphere.copernicus.org/preprints/2025/egusphere-2025-4954/. This dataset is available for download and use.</p> <p>Dataset x: "Field study Zurich". The data was generated in activity A3.2.4 to identify N₂O isotopic composition emitted from agricultural soil. This data was used to achieve objective 4. This dataset is available on https://meta.icos-cp.eu/objects/Gyy707SMePiDDIFUCt8Du2Cq. This dataset is under embargo and will be available for download and preview after 2026-05-31.</p>
16 Will the data be accessible through a free and standardised access protocol?	Yes, Zenodo provides well described conditions for free and standardised access (see http://about.zenodo.org/policies/).
17 If there are restrictions on use, how will access be provided to the data, both during and after the end of the project?	There are no restrictions on the use of the published data, but users are required to acknowledge the project and the source of the data in any resulting publications, according to the CC-BY 4.0 license.
18 How will the identity of the person accessing the data be ascertained?	User registration requirements on repositories (e.g. Zenodo) ensure recording of the identities of those accessing the data.
19 Is there a need for a data access committee (e.g. to evaluate/approve access requests to personal/sensitive data)?	This consortium does not have a Data Access Committee, because the project is not going to produce sensitive data. All results are publicly available without restrictions
Metadata:	
20 Will metadata be made openly available and licensed under a public domain dedication CC0, as per the Grant Agreement? If not, please clarify why. Will metadata contain information to enable the user to access the data?	In Zenodo, metadata are licensed under CC0, except for email addresses. All metadata are exported via OAI-PMH and can be harvested.
21 How long will the data remain available and findable? Will metadata be guaranteed to remain available after data are no longer available?	<p>The data will remain available and findable for the lifetime of the Zenodo repository, which is expected to be a minimum of 20 years.</p> <p>If data are withdrawn from Zenodo, the DOI and the URL of the original object are retained. In case of closure of the Zenodo repository, best efforts will be made by Zenodo to integrate all content into suitable alternative institutional and/or subject based repositories.</p>
22 Will documentation or reference about any software be needed to access or read the data and will this be included? Will it be possible to include the relevant software (e.g. in open source code)?	The public datasets are in a common format (CSV, TXT and MS Excel) and can be read using widely available software (open source or commercial such as MS office) and specialised scientific software (open source or commercial such as Matlab and Mathematica).

1.2.3 Making data interoperable

Questions	Answers
23 What data and metadata vocabularies, standards, formats or methodologies will you follow to make your data interoperable to allow data exchange and re-use within and across disciplines? Will you follow community-endorsed interoperability best practices? Which ones?	<p>The datasets use the trusted repository's basic metadata schema for administrative data, which is compliant with the recommended standards used by DataCite (https://search.datacite.org/) and OpenAIRE (https://www.basemsearch.net/). For individual datasets, the following discipline-specific vocabularies, standards, formats, and methodologies have been used:</p> <ol style="list-style-type: none"> 1. GUM (procedure; subject-independent). 2. OBO foundry (MD schema; biological sciences). 3. DICOM (MD schema + file format; biomedical imaging). 4. NetCDF (file container format; geographical information). 5. HDF5 (hierarchical file format; subject-independent). 6. CityGML (file format; smart city). 7. INSPEC (vocabulary + classification; physics). 8. ISO 9001 (QM procedure; subject-independent).
24 In case it is unavoidable that you use uncommon or generate project specific ontologies or vocabularies, will you provide mappings to more commonly used ontologies? Will you openly publish the generated ontologies or vocabularies to allow their re-use, refinement or extension?	Mapping is not required as the terminology used is chosen to be compatible with the existing literature.
25 Will your data include qualified references ¹ to other data (e.g. other data from your project, or datasets from previous research)?	No, the project's datasets is not including any references to other data.

1.2.4 Increase data re-use

Questions	Answers
26 How will you provide documentation needed to validate data analysis and facilitate data re-use (e.g. readme files with information on methodology, codebooks, data cleaning, analyses, variable definitions, units of measurement, etc.)?	A short README file (e.g. Markdown) is provided together with the data, in order to enable data analysis and to facilitate data re-use.
27 Will your data be made freely available in the public domain to permit the widest re-use possible? Will your data be licensed using standard re-use licenses, in line with the	The data are either licensed under the latest available version of the Creative Commons Attribution International Public License (CC BY) or a license with equivalent rights as set out in the Grant Agreement. Users are required to acknowledge the consortium and the source of the data in any resulting publications. Alternatively, the Creative Commons Public Domain Dedication License (CC 0) is used.

¹ A qualified reference is a cross-reference that explains its intent. For example, X is regulator of Y is a much more qualified reference than X is associated with Y, or X see also Y. The goal therefore is to create as many meaningful links as possible between (meta)data resources to enrich the contextual knowledge about the data. (Source: <https://www.qo-fair.org/fair-principles/i3-metadata-include-qualified-references-metadata/>)

Questions	Answers
obligations set out in the Grant Agreement?	
28 Will the data produced in the project be useable by third parties, in particular after the end of the project?	Any data published in open-access journals is usable by third parties after the datasets have been deposited in Zenodo. The data that do not relate to peer-reviewed publications is made available for re-use on a case-by-case basis.
29 Will the provenance of the data be thoroughly documented using the appropriate standards?	Yes, the provenance and context of the data is thoroughly documented to meet relevant standards using the Provenance and Context Content Standard (PCCS) Matrix. Data are accompanied by information on how they were captured, processed, analysed, and validated. Other information that enables interpretation and use are also provided.
30 Describe all relevant data quality assurance processes.	Data quality is assured through several quality assurance procedures: <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Repeated and comparison measurements. • Adherence to standards for data recording. • Use of controlled vocabularies and standard terminology. • Metrological characterisation of the measurement set-ups. • Validation of the data collected. • Provision of test results along with the data. • Peer-review of publications based on the data.
31 Further to the FAIR principles, DMPs should also address research outputs other than data, and should carefully consider aspects related to the allocation of resources, data security and ethical aspects.	<p><i>Allocation of resources</i></p> <p>The estimated costs for making the (data and) other research outputs FAIR are 1 000 € (personnel costs) (see question 34). The costs for making other research outputs FAIR are included in the project's budget and have been claimed if compliant with the Grant Agreement's conditions. Where feasible, long-term preservation is ensured by depositing the other research outputs in repositories. The Data Access Committee has decided on a case-by-case basis on which other research outputs have to be deposited and for how long.</p> <p><i>Security of other research outputs</i></p> <p>All participants are either accredited to, or work in compliance with, the ISO 17025 standard on the "General requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories". The participants store other research outputs on their organisations' networks, which are protected by firewall, backups etc. Other research outputs are also stored in the project's SharePoint environment, with password-protected login. Deposition in public repositories provides additional security as they have multiple replicas in a distributed file system which is backed up on a nightly basis. This project has not generated sensitive other research outputs. The other research outputs are safely stored in open access repositories.</p> <p><i>Ethical aspects</i></p> <p>There are issues that could impact on the sharing of other research outputs.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Information relating to other research outputs acquired from third parties, e.g. manufacturers, are not shared without their explicit consent. • Information relating to other research outputs collected by the consortium at commercial sites are not shared without the site owner's explicit consent. <p>Ethical issues have been addressed as the project has prepared an ethics report. The project has not shared other research outputs with identifiable personal information. Sensitive information relating to the other research outputs have been collected, separated as soon as</p>

Questions	Answers
	possible and kept secure. Please also see the information provided in section 1.3 below.

1.3 Other research outputs

Questions	Answers
32 In addition to the management of data, beneficiaries should also consider and plan for the management of other research outputs that may be generated or re-used throughout their projects. Such outputs can be either digital (e.g. software, workflows, protocols, models, etc.) or physical (e.g. new materials, antibodies, reagents, samples, etc.).	The new calibration methods, and protocols produced by the project are stored in the Protocol Exchange repository. The management of the IP issues surrounding the new materials that have been developed in the project have been planned for in the project's consortium agreement. The consortium intends to seek patent protection. This project has only re-used existing data and has not re-used any other research outputs.
33 Beneficiaries should consider which of the questions pertaining to FAIR data above, can apply to the management of other research outputs, and should strive to provide sufficient detail on how their research outputs will be managed and shared, or made available for re-use, in line with the FAIR principles.	As far as possible, the FAIR data approaches specified in questions 7-30 above have been applied to the management of this project's other research outputs. This commitment has been met by releasing the new software that will be developed in the project under license, by placing the new calibration methods, and protocols, in a repository and by patenting the new materials that have been developed in the project in line with the requirements of the project's consortium agreement.

1.4 Allocation of resources

Questions	Answers
34 What will the costs be for making data or other research outputs FAIR in your project (e.g. direct and indirect costs related to storage, archiving, re-use, security, etc.) ?	The estimated costs for making the data and other research outputs Findable, Accessible, Interoperable and Re-usable (FAIR) are 1 000 € (personnel costs). These costs have been kept to a minimum by using a free repository (Zenodo) and by making only relevant data and other outputs FAIR.
35 How will these be covered? Note that costs related to research data/output management are eligible as part of the European partnership on metrology grant (if compliant with the Grant Agreement conditions).	The costs for making the data FAIR are included in the project's budget and have been claimed if compliant with the Grant Agreement's conditions.
36 Who will be responsible for data management in your project?	The consortium's Data Access Committee has overall responsibility for data management. The coordinator leads this committee and is responsible for coordinating updates to the data management plan. The committee is responsible for organising data backup and storage, data archiving and for depositing the data within the repositories (Zenodo, PTB's Open Access Repository).

37 How will long term preservation be ensured? Discuss the necessary resources to accomplish this (costs and potential value, who decides and how, what data will be kept and for how long)?	Long term preservation has been ensured by depositing the data within repositories (Zenodo). There are no costs associated with the long-term preservation of the data in these repositories. The data will increase in value over time because of its fundamental impact in a wide range of applications. It will enable the technologies developed in the project to be taken up by the measurement supply chain and by standards bodies. These standards bodies will need access to the data to justify the robustness of future standards. The data will also be of value as it underpins the results of published datasets.
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1.5 Data security

Questions	Answers
38 What provisions are or will be in place for data security (including data recovery as well as secure storage/archiving and transfer of sensitive data)?	<p><i>Data recovery and secure storage</i></p> <p>All participants either are accredited to, or work in compliance with, the ISO 17025 standard on the “General requirements for the competence of testing and calibration laboratories”. The participants store data on their organisations’ networks, which are protected by firewall, backups etc. Data is also being stored in the project’s SharePoint environment, with password protected login. Deposition in the Zenodo public repository will provide additional security as it has multiple replicas in a distributed file system which is backed up on a nightly basis. This project has not generated sensitive data.</p>
39 Will the data be safely stored in trusted repositories for long term preservation and curation?	Yes, the data are safely stored in the Zenodo open access repository. Zenodo and the underlying Invenio Framework for digital repositories were designed according to the Open Archival Information Systems (OAIS) reference model. Zenodo is working towards ISO 16363 certification.

1.6 Ethics

Questions	Answers
40 Are there, or could there be, any ethics or legal issues that can have an impact on data sharing? These can also be discussed in the context of the ethics review. If relevant, include references to ethics report(s) and the ethics section in the Annex 1.	<p>There are issues that could impact on data sharing.</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • Data acquired from third parties, e.g. manufacturers, will not be shared without their explicit consent. • Data collected by the consortium at commercial sites will not be shared without the site owner’s explicit consent. • The data from the market surveys have been made anonymous to comply with the General Data Protection Regulation (GDPR). Ethical issues have been addressed as the project has prepared and submit a report on the Dual Use of the project’s results.
41 Will informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation be included in questionnaires dealing with personal data?	Informed consent for data sharing and long-term preservation have been included in the market and customer surveys, but the project had no plans to share data with identifiable personal information.

1.7 Other issues

Questions	Answers
42 Do you, or will you, make use of other national / funder / sectorial / departmental procedures for data management? If yes, which	<p>Data management was compliant with:</p> <ul style="list-style-type: none"> • The research data policy of the European Partnership on Metrology; • European laws about data security and the protection of privacy (e.g. GDPR); • Institutional guidelines; • Scientific community guidelines.

ones (please list and briefly describe them)?	
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2 Open science: research data management

Statement	Put an X in the box to confirm	Or, list any exceptions to this
All participants have adhered to the requirements of the project's GA and CA with respect to open science: research data management (GA Article 17 and its Annex 5) for this reporting period	☒	

